

AMBIDEXTERITY AND IT COMPETENCE CAN IMPROVE SUPPLY CHAIN FLEXIBILITY? A RESOURCE ORCHESTRATION APPROACH

Abstract

Supply chain flexibility (SCF) has become an important competitive weapon for companies in the current dynamic environment. This paper explores the influence of ambidexterity on supply chain flexibility (SCF) and theorizes the moderating effect of information technology (IT) competence on that relationship. Whereas prior research focuses on the positive results of SCF for business performance, little empirical research has studied its facilitators, leaving the gap this study seeks to fill. We draw on resource orchestration theory to develop our research model. According to this theory, a firm can exploit the full potential of its resources and capabilities only when these are deployed in a complementary manner. This study proposes that ambidexterity impacts SCF positively and that its effect is amplified when the firm possesses IT competence. In order to test our hypotheses we have employed a hierarchical regression methodology and put into service data collected from manufacturing enterprises. The study confirms that ambidexterity, as the ability to explore and exploit SC resources, enables their orchestration, making SC resources flexible, and a high IT competence facilitates that orchestration.

Keywords: Ambidexterity; Supply chain flexibility; IT competence; Resource orchestration theory.

1. Introduction

Supply chain flexibility (SCF) has been identified as one of the more relevant topics in research on supply chain management (SCM). Having a flexible supply chain (SC) is key to gaining and maintaining a sustained competitive advantage in the current environment, one characterized by dynamism, uncertainty, and unpredictability (Braunscheidel and Suresh, 2009; Gunasekaran et al. 2001).

As a result, a significant body of literature has emerged to study SCF. While extensive, the research has so far focused on the benefits a firm reaps by developing a flexible SC; the positive effect of a flexible SC on firm performance is widely recognized (Ngai et al. 2011; Chavez et al., 2017). However, a significant gap exists in the literature: few studies offer a deeper understanding of the strategies and practices that facilitate SCF (Rojo et al., 2018).

When contemplating the situations in which SCF is considered a source of competitive advantage, such as in the cases of Amazon, Wal-Mart, or UPS, we can verify that SCF is due not to any single asset or capacity but is the result of combining knowledge assets and capabilities, including information technologies (Ellram et al., 2013). Thus, this study aims to analyze which blend of those resources related to knowledge management better enables firms to develop a flexible SC.

To make such a determination precisely and accurately, we must first scrutinize the effect of SC ambidexterity on SCF. SC ambidexterity is the simultaneous implementation of practices that exploit current knowledge and explore or create new knowledge (Kristal et al. 2010; March, 1991). Although the benefits of ambidexterity at the organizational level have been widely researched (O'Reilly and Tushman, 2013), they have received very little study in SC operations (Patel et al., 2012; Arlbjøn and Mikkelsen, 2014). Evidence exists to show that better adaptation to the environment is achieved through the amassing of knowledge by way of exploration and exploitation (McNiff, 2000; Santos-Vijande et al., 2012). An essential requirement to achieving environmental adaptation is flexibility (Krajewski et al., 2005). Therefore, it is proposed that the strategy of ambidexterity will have a positive effect on SCF.

Then, the positive moderating effect of IT competence on the relationship between SC ambidexterity and SCF must be analyzed. A study of IT competencies is necessary because knowledge management is an IT-driven capability, and changes in IT may influence the outcomes of knowledge management (Setia and Patel, 2013). An empirical study is needed to understand the mechanisms underlying IT capabilities in this context (Ray et al., 2005; Wu et al., 2006), both because it is common business practice to use different ITs in SCM (Fawcett et al., 2011) and because little is known about how IT competence enables superior performance in the SC.

We ground our model in resource orchestration theory (ROT), an extension of the resource-based view and dynamic capabilities theory (Sirmon et al., 2011). The core of this theory argues that managers must orchestrate firm resources the way a conductor orchestrates the instruments in the orchestra to obtain a competitive advantage (Liu et al., 2016). The goal of this theoretical framework is to help managers predict *ex ante* specific resource combinations that will obtain a competitive advantage (Sirmon et al., 2007).

Resource orchestration theory is especially precise for understanding the complementary effect of SC ambidexterity and IT competence on developing SCF. Wade and Hulland (2004, p.109) hold that “information systems exert their influence on the firm through complementary relationships with other firm assets and capabilities”. The effect of IT competence on organizations is thus argued to occur through other organizational capabilities and assets (Oh et al., 2012). Specifically, the influence of ambidexterity on SCF will be strengthened in the presence of IT competence, as the latter facilitates greater coordination in management of the knowledge obtained through exploration and exploitation due to increased speed in perceiving change and adapting SC connections (Gosain et al., 2005).

A study of this type is especially important both because managers are often unfamiliar with supporting inputs (such as IT competence) that bundle with strategic input to sustain the organization’s success and because this lack of knowledge is even greater in the SCM context (Ellram et al., 2013). Put simply, the main objective is to determine how firms can combine assets and competences related to knowledge management, i.e., how to configure the firm’s portfolio to help it build SCF.

Thus, there are four contributions this article seeks to make to the literature of IT and SCM. The first two are to deepen understanding of the implementation of ambidexterity in the context of SC as well to analyse how it influences SCF. The third one is to study the moderating effect of IT competence on this relationship. The last but not least to use ROT to explain the proposed relationships and the complementarity of ambidexterity and IT competence in development of SCF.

To discuss these research objectives, from this point onwards the article structure is the following: Section 2 details the theoretical principles on the proposed model is based as well as the integrating hypotheses. Section 3 describes the methods and analyses conducted. Finally, Section 4 presents the results and a discussion of them as well as confirming the study’s conclusions, identifying its constraints, and suggesting new possible research directions.

2. Theoretical framework and hypotheses development

2.1. Resource Orchestration Theory

Resource orchestration theory (ROT) is a broad, theoretical framework that integrates an extended resource-based view and dynamic capabilities theory into a single theoretical corpus that overcomes the limitations of each. Both the resource-based view and dynamic capabilities theory argue that assets, resources, and capabilities that are valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable are a source of competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). Although both theories identify requirements that the capabilities and resources must satisfy if they are to be a source of competitive advantage, neither theory explains how firms can develop these capabilities and resources. ROT fills this gap by stressing that the most important factor is managers' structuring a firm's portfolio of resources and bundling them to build capabilities that realize their firm's competitive advantage (Helfat et al., 2007; Sirmon et al., 2007; 2011).

For Hitt et al. (2016), the most important factor in business management is not the mere identification of the best combination of assets and capabilities but the way they are coordinated and synchronized by management. Practices can be imitated, but it is difficult to imitate a set of capabilities, and even more difficult to imitate the way these capabilities are synchronized.

ROT views a firm as a set of assets, resources, and capabilities where the development of sustainable competitive advantage depends on managers' skill in generating synergistic effects through the deployment of resources and capabilities (Helfat et al., 2007; Sirmon et al., 2007). But the capability to generate synergies depends on the potential complementarity of the resources as well as on a firm's effectiveness in orchestrating resources within and across firm boundaries (Baert et al., 2016).

Initially, ROT was developed at the firm level, but authors such as Ellram et al. (2013) have emphasized the fact that, "increasingly, supply chain resources are part of that strategic bundle of resources essential for achieving the firm's competitive advantage" (p. 29). More recently, Wowak et al. (2016) note that ROT stresses the need to transcend firm boundaries to obtain and manage SC resources. In fact, Sirmon et al. (2011) indicate that the next step in developing ROT is to expand its reach by using resource orchestration beyond the firm itself. This study is doing precisely that by expanding ROT's explanatory power for use in the context of a firm's SC.

2.2. Supply Chain ambidexterity: the ability to explore and exploit SC resources

The concept of ambidexterity has attracted considerable interest in organizational theory, thereby becoming one of the paradigms for current research (Turner et al., 2013; Stettner and Lavie, 2014). Ambidexterity is understood to be the ability to make the most of existing knowledge while simultaneously generating new knowledge (Levinthal and March, 1993; March, 1991) with the intent of achieving a competitive advantage (Turner et al., 2013). Since the concepts of ambidexterity and absorptive capacity have been widely used in the SCM literature

(eg Patel et al., 2012; Kristal et al. 2010; Rojo et al., 2016; Rojo et al. 2018), and these concepts may have some similarities in their definitions, we have summarized in the Appendix A the main definitions given for both concepts with the object of differentiating them.

The first studies of ambidexterity focused on determining whether exploration and exploitation practices could be compatible. Older studies held that the tasks or routines required for exploiting existing knowledge differ completely from those employed to explore new knowledge, and they warned about the risks of falling into “failure traps” and “success traps” (Levinthal and March, 1993). But subsequent studies have shown the compatibility of the two (Cao et al., 2009).

More recent studies consider exploration and exploitation to be two components of the same learning process. Since this compatibility has been demonstrated, current research focuses on analyzing its benefits, which have been demonstrated at the level of the organization, business unit, project, alliance and individual (Birkinshaw and Gupta, 2013; O’Reilly and Tushman, 2013). But little study in the SC has been conducted (Gualandris et al., 2018). Our study develops a deeper understanding of SC ambidexterity. This study adopts the conceptualization by Kristal et al. (2010) of SC ambidexterity as the calculated choices a manufacturing company makes via its managing body to pursue at the same time supply chain exploration as well as exploitation practices. In other words, SC ambidexterity can be framed as the firm’s ability to explore and exploit SC resources simultaneously, that is, as the manager’s capability (Turner et al., 2013) to integrate and reconfigure both the firm’s and SC partners’ resources through exploration and exploitation. Through resource exploration, the firm identifies new ways to diversify its product offerings or to develop new uses for existing resources. Through resource exploitation, in contrast, the firm pursues efficiency in its existing operations (Sirmon et al., 2011). The most important resources in need of management to develop ambidexterity have been categorized as organizational capital, social capital, and human capital resources (for an in-depth review, see Turner et al., 2013).

This strategy is justified by the fact that it is easy to implement ambidexterity in organizational networks (Kristal et al., 2010) because doing so involves combining the organization’s own knowledge with external knowledge and the SC is “the network of organizations that are involved, through upstream and downstream linkages, in the different processes and activities that produce value in the form of products and services in the hands of the ultimate consumer”(Christopher, 2005 p. 17). Along these lines, O’Reilly and Tushman (2013) claim that research on ambidexterity should extend it to the firm’s strategy and the agents with which it interacts, not be limited to the firm itself.

Originally, ambidexterity was considered a subset of organizational learning, but lately it has come to refer to managerial tension or paradox (Turner et al., 2013; Koryak et al., 2018). This study uses ambidexterity in the earlier sense. In fact, ambidexterity has been studied from

different perspectives, including knowledge management (Tamayo-Torres et al., 2014), which is why exploration and exploitation reflect different learning orientations (Koryak et al., 2018). Whereas exploration is learning via modifications of the processes as well as organized experiments or various test types, exploitation is expounded as a company's acquisition of knowledge by seeking information, selection, processing and the betterment of existing routines through experience (Baum et al., 2000). Supplier qualification, supplier development, and automation of cross-organizational tasks (automated billing, report preparation, inventory management, etc.) (Kristal et al., 2010; Gualandris et al., 2018) are typical examples of exploitation applied to SC resources. Examples of SC resources exploration practices might be supplier innovation workshops and the employment of systems for cross-entity business intelligence (Kristal et al., 2010; Gualandris et al., 2018).

2.3. Supply Chain Flexibility: orchestration of SC resources

The current business environment, which is characterized by uncertain demand and a high degree of volatility, presents a challenge for SCM, as it demands that firms possess flexible SCs capable of rapidly adapting to supply disruptions and abrupt alterations in demand without disrupting services to customers (Stevenson and Spring, 2007). Tachizawa and Gimenez (2009) define SCF as the ability of a firm's purchasing function to respond effectively, rapidly, and at the lowest cost possible to modify requirements for components it buys in terms of volume, mix, and delivery date. Despite the variety of conceptualizations of SCF, all theoretical definitions define it as the capability of SCs to respond to environmental changes in a timely manner. SCF and SC resilience are related terms in SC literature, since these concepts may have some similarities in their definitions, we have included in Appendix B, a summary table to differentiate the terms and meanings of both concepts.

Various theoretical models have defined the dimensions of SCF (Stevenson and Spring, 2007; Manders et al. 2017), and as a consequence, two problems arise that increase the difficulty of clearly distinguishing between the dimensions necessarily required for flexibility in manufacturing and supply chain flexibility. Because of this difficulty, the effort to create a measurement scale that operationalizes the conceptualizations has failed (Manders et al., 2017). This study resolves the difficulty by adopting the model advanced by Moon et al. (2012).

According to Moon et al. (2012), SCF is a construct comprised of: sourcing flexibility, defined as having the dexterity to acquire available materials and service in the midst of fluctuating conditions; operating system flexibility, conceived of as the ability to offer products that have a sufficiently extensive range of attributes that the specifications of any customer can be met; distribution flexibility, viewed as the capability of an organization to efficiently manage

its distributors, storage and loading facilities, and other components of its distribution system; and information system flexibility, which refers to having an information system flexible enough to react quickly to changing conditions in the market, especially those involving unanticipated misfits.

A flexible SC has dual functions. It reacts to changing market conditions while simultaneously playing a strategic role (Rojo et al., 2016). In fluid market conditions organizations that have developed the flexibility of their SCs are likely to harvest competitive advantages from both functions (Gerwin, 1993). Gerwin (1993) underscores the notion that SCF not only enables rapid and effective adaptation to changing market conditions but also creates uncertainties that competitors cannot challenge. There is nearly unanimous agreement in the literature that SCF has a positive effect on organizational performance (Blome et al., 2013; Martínez Sánchez and Pérez Pérez, 2005; Swink et al., 2005). But the mechanisms creating this positive effect have been under-researched. That SCF precedes firm benefits and is a source of competitive advantage has been adequately demonstrated, so research must now focus on identifying which strategies and mechanisms produce these results (Rojo et al., 2018). Prior research has identified some antecedents of SCF such as supplier development, supplier partnering, JIT purchasing (Scannell et al., 2000), operational absorptive capacity, organisational learning (Rojo et al., 2018), information sharing (Schmenner and Tatikonda, 2005) and information systems (White et al., 2005). Nevertheless, these type of studies are scarce and did not provide a solid theoretical framework that explain how SCF is developed. This article seeks to fill this gap using ROT. From the perspective of ROT, SCF can be viewed as orchestration of SC resources and partners, that is, as “the process by which managers make, build, acquire, deploy, and redeploy decisions with respect to” (Pitelis and Teece, 2010, p.1254) SC assets and suppliers in order to produce a timely and appropriate SC response to environmental dynamism. This conceptualization agrees with both Zhu et al. (2020), who conceive of SCF as the extent to which a firm can easily and readily orchestrate these linkages throughout its SC, and the case study by Schriber and Löwstedt (2018), who conclude that flexibility is a capability that results from orchestration of different assets.

2.4 Effect of SC ambidexterity on SCF

Even though ambidexterity started by being studied in operations and supply chain management (Kristal et al., 2010; Rojo et al., 2016), the true nature of the connections between SC ambidexterity and SC together with SCF has yet to be focused on . There is a recent pioneering study by Adler et al. (2009), which advocated the improvement of long term flexibility through the combination of both exploitation as well as exploration in the operating processes of the firm.

SCF enables an organization to respond immediately to unexpected market changes. Thus it is important that an organization be able to learn continually so that it is prepared for any challenge from its environment (Ngai et al., 2011). Organizations that learn from current competences and activities (exploitation) while simultaneously integrating this knowledge with knowledge from outside the organization and putting new abilities into practice (exploration) can learn from their customers, competitors, and market situation. Such learning facilitates early recognition of unforeseen changes and market trends and reaction to them (Tippins and Sohi, 2003). Hernández-Espallardo et al. (2010) also show the importance of learning and sharing knowledge along SCs.

The ability to precisely record, at a convenient time, relevant data which predicts market tendencies and recognizes the need to eliminate routines that no longer serve a function, is a direct result of the learning capability that certain organizational units possess. Popadiuk (2012) suggests that the ease of adaptation to never before seen circumstances is stimulated through the process of learning which has its origins in the successful melding of exploration and exploitation. According to Khazanchi et al. (2007) units that encourage both exploration and exploitation simultaneously are characterized by a high capacity to adaptation to the environment.

Gosain et al. (2005) demonstrate empirically that the companies that comprise the SC to become highly proficient in rapid adaptation; knowledge acquisition facilitates adaptation to the environment and the other SC members. Likewise, Beer et al. (2005) and Lumpkin and Lichtenstein (2005) recognize the role that learning plays in strengthening a firm's ability to recognize opportunities and adapt continually to the environment. Consistent with the literature, this study proposes that implementing learning practices based both on refinement and perfection of existing routines and competences (exploitation practices) and on the testing and addition of new routines and competences (exploration practices) produces a recombination of internal and external knowledge that leads to improvement in SCF. We thus formulate the first study hypothesis:

H1: Supply chain ambidexterity is positively associated with supply chain flexibility.

2.5 Moderating effect of IT competence on the relationship between Supply Chain ambidexterity and Supply Chain Flexibility: IT competence facilitates orchestration of SC resources

Tippins and Sohi (2003, p. 748) assert that IT competence represents the degree to which a firm possess IT knowledge and uses that knowledge effectively to manage information generated in the firm. As conceptualized by these authors, IT competence is composed of three dimensions. The first is IT knowledge, which refers to the extent to which a firm possesses a body

of technical knowledge of IT objects. This is technical knowledge that can be identified with the firm's IT know-how. The second is IT operations, the extent to which a firm uses IT to manage market and consumer information. This dimension refers to the operations, techniques, activities, and abilities that demonstrate a firm's technical knowledge in IT. The third dimension is related to IT objects, which include software, hardware, and support personnel, IT tools all because they enable the acquisition, processing, storing, dissemination, and use of the information. Taken together, these three dimensions represent the firm's specialized resources and are indicative of its ability to understand and employ IT tools and processes to manage information from the market and its customers.

The role of IT competence in performance has been debated at length in the literature. Initially, the literature indicated that IT competence was a variable that could by itself improve performance. The most recent research stream is unanimous, however, in stressing that this positive effect always occurs through complementary relationships with other factors or capabilities (Mikalef and Pateli, 2017). In other words, IT competence deploys its effects only through other capabilities (Wamba et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2013; Rai et al., 2006; Oh et al., 2012). Within SCM, the results of studies on this issue are mixed. Some studies report that investment in IT competence improves SC performance such as SCF, but others fail to find this effect, or they argue that such investment can have a negative effect on performance (Zhang et al., 2016).

From the perspective of ROT, the fact that assets and capabilities such as IT competence are essential elements of the firm portfolio for developing SCF must be analyzed. This theoretical framework explains why IT competence improves performance in some cases but not in others or, on occasion, has negative effects, as this variable's effect depends on combining assets and capabilities. Yao and Zhu (2012) argue that "alignment between IT and SC processes can help firms improve their operations. Such alignment generates transactional efficiencies, which may further create operational and strategic benefits" (p. 1047). Moreover, by integrating IT competence into SC operations, firms can increase the difficulty of imitation due to the interconnectedness of the integrated resources (Oh et al., 2012). Prior research notes the importance of bundling IT competence with other capabilities to achieve a competitive advantage in SCM (Chiang et al., 2012; Sacristán-Díaz et al., 2018). In this view, ROT could be used to propose that firms' ability to translate SC ambidexterity into heightened SCF depends on their ability to leverage IT competence in conjunction with SC ambidexterity (Liu et al., 2016). In addition, managerial IT competence facilitates orchestration of SC resources, allocating them in a flexible way. In other words, IT competence enables firms to derive knowledge from exploration and exploitation of SC resources and facilitates orchestration of these resources, resulting in responsiveness to market changes (Liu et al., 2016). We posit that IT competence allows firms to orchestrate their resources more efficiently and effectively. This managerial competence helps to

heighten the efficacy of the firm's resource bundling efforts because it helps practitioners to improve their decision-making processes and perspectives due to quicker access to critical market information (Wales et al., 2013). Along these lines, Queiroz et al. (2018) recently demonstrated the potential of IT competence to facilitate orchestration of resources at firm level.

As SC ambidexterity entails two components, we find it essential to examine the effects of both SC exploration and SC exploitation on SCF in the presence of IT competence. IT competence enhances SC exploration by helping a firm acquire and assimilate knowledge from SC partners and other departments in a firm. It does this by enhancing technical coordination and informative coordination in a firm. It improves the former by helping with the synchronization of different data standards and connecting communication networks across organizations (Setia and Patel, 2013). Greater technical coordination produces closer relationships among SC members and makes acquisition of knowledge from SC partners more reliable and efficient. Informative coordination refers to uniformity in information exchanges among different agents inside and outside an organization (Setia and Patel, 2013). IT competence improves informative coordination by enabling boundary-spanning processes across a firm's network (Dewet and Jones, 2001) and with processes that integrate knowledge acquisition and improve shared meaning in knowledge transfer. When access is uniform and meaning shared, the resulting knowledge becomes more effective than the knowledge otherwise would have been (Szulanski, 1996; Zahra and George, 2002). This result is especially important in exploration practices in the SC, a network in which each member firm has its own organizational culture and know-how, which makes having a shared vision of quality, speed, and so on difficult (Skarholt et al., 2016) and ultimately hinders knowledge exploration processes. IT competence helps firms integrate knowledge acquired via exploration and enables them to combine information provided by customers, suppliers, and distributors, information that can facilitate a product change, service, and delivery mix (Oh et al., 2012), which in turn affect SCF.

Vital for knowledge exploitation in organizational networks, IT competence amplifies SC exploitation by improving strategic coordination. Its development depends on discussions with SC partners (Setia and Patel, 2013) and entails the coordination of multiple interested parties (suppliers and distributors) who have their own business interests. Firms possessing IT competence are in the best position to facilitate these discussions with such activities as e-brainstorming, collaborative learning, e-meetings, and so on that can improve strategic coordination (Gallupe et al., 1992; Alavi, 1994; Dennis et al., 1988; Setia and Patel, 2013). In addition, a firm's infrastructure and resources-sharing with SC partners (e.g., inventories shared to reap pooling benefits) (Oh et al., 2012) are enhanced by a combination of exploitation practices and IT competence, which together make a firm's SC more flexible. Thus, we propose the following hypothesis:

H2: IT competence positively moderates the relationship between supply chain ambidexterity and supply chain flexibility.

Figure 1 represents visually the interconnections submitted for empirical verification within the model proposed

Figure 1: Theoretical model

3. Methodology

3.1. Data collection and sampling

A survey was constructed that would collect information on exploration and exploitation practices, SCF, and IT competence as well as relevant demographics on firms and respondents. Most of the answers used a seven-point Likert scale. The instrument was developed utilizing the Moore and Benbasat (1991) procedure to ensure its content validity.

The sample for this study was a set of Spanish manufacturing firms listed in the 2014 SABI database, which contains 45,166 firms. Only manufacturing firms that boast a full registry of data have been included and we obtained a sample of 2,517 firms. The surveys were addressed to the individuals in charge of the firm's SC or, if this position did not exist, to those in charge of purchasing or the manager. The response rate was of twelve per cent. Table 1 shows the traits of the informants and firms of which the sample is comprised. The manufacturing sector was chosen for this study due to its importance to the Spanish economy. It represents 14% of GDP and is the

second most important sector of the economy. It is also a source of long-term competitiveness thanks to its stimulating effect on other sectors. Thus, when there is a one euro increase in the final demand of the manufacturing sector, there is an increase in the production value of the whole economy by 3.11 euros¹. Our sample reflects the diversity of the Spanish manufacturing industry in terms of:

❖ firm size² with

- 10-49 employees → 46.20% of firms
- 50-250 → 35.52%
- 251-1000 → 15.51%
- over 1000 → 2.77%

and (in the same order as seen in Table 1)

❖ economic activity

- 24.71% food, beverage and tobacco products → 24.71%
- 10.08% textiles and apparel,
- 6.11 % chemical and pharmaceutical,
- 12.8% plastics,
- 1.86% computers, electronics and optics,
- 2.87% electrical equipment,
- 30.11% machinery and equipment,
- 4.58% furniture,
- 4.02% automotive
- 2.83% other industries.

An U test of Mann-Whitney was performed to test whether significant differences existed between the distribution of the sample and that of the target population. The results ($\alpha=0.05$) show that the sample does not differ significantly from the population industry distribution. To analyze for nonresponse bias, we compared the first (n= 170) and last responses (n= 132) to determine that there were no significant differences between them, thus it appears there was no significant nonresponse bias.

¹ Confederation of Employers and Industries of Spain report:
https://contenidos.ceoe.es/CEOE/var/pool/pdf/publications_docs-file-442-la-industria-motor-de-crecimiento-analisis-y-propuestas.pdf

² Information retrieved from the Spanish National Statistics Institute (INE):
https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/categoria.htm?c=Estadistica_P&cid=1254735576550

Table 1: Characteristics of the sample

	N	Percentage (%)
Informant		
SC Manager	81	26.82
Production Dept. Manager	130	43.05
Manager	91	30.13
Total	302	100
Manufacturing industry ¹		
Food, beverage, and tobacco products	3	1
Textiles and apparel	5	1.65
Chemical and pharmaceutical	26	8.61
Plastics	28	9.27
Computers, electronics, and optics	23	7.61
Electrical equipment	30	9.93
Machinery and equipment	110	36.42
Furniture	47	15.57
Automotive	25	8.29
Other	5	1.65
Total	302	100
Firm size (no. employees)		
10-49	69	22.85
50-250	142	47.02
251-1000	58	19.20
Over 1000	33	10.93
Total	302	100

¹According to the International Standard Industrial Classification of All Economic Activities (ISIC).

3.2 Measurement scales

Multi-item scales developed in the Management literature to measure SC ambidexterity, SCF and IT competence were employed in this study. Supply chain ambidexterity was measured using exploration and exploitation of the SC following the 8-item scale proposed by Kristal et al. (2010). SCF was measured using the 13-item scale developed by Moon et al. (2012). Finally, IT competence was assessed by adjusting the 15-item scale suggested by Tippins and Sohi (2003). This manner of conceptualizing IT competence has the advantage of avoiding the main difficulties involved in study of ITs which derive from the following issues: 1) new IT tools are being developed continually, and as new technologies are generalized and made available to firms, the results of studies that utilized older technologies become useless, and 2) many of the advantages that firms obtain through adoption of a specific IT system are of short duration, since these advantages disappear when the technologies are generalized or become obsolete (Tippins and Sohi, 2003). The Appendix C includes a detailed presentation of the items employed in the study.

The SPSS v.20 was used to calculate the EFA as a first step before a confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) was conducted. Appendix D shows the results of the analysis performed where 8 factors with a value higher than 1.0 were produced. Said constructs account for 74.171% of the variance of the data and were the ones expected.

We evaluated the scales utilizing confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) with EQS 6.0 software. Scale reliability was assessed through composite reliability (CR), average variance extracted (AVE), and Cronbach's Alpha (Hair et al., 2010). The constructs' CR values were above the recommended minimum of 0.70 (Bagozzi & Yi, 1988), and the AVEs above 0.5 (see Table 2). These statistics conform to the criteria proposed by Fornell and Larcker (1981). The reliability indicated by the Cronbach's Alpha coefficients, which evaluate the constructs' internal consistency, also exceeded the recommended minimum of 0.70 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994). The results presented in Table 2 thus confirm internal consistency and reliability of all scales.

Table 2: CFA of the measurement scales

Item	Factor loadings	t-value	R2	Scale reliability
Exploration				
Exlr1	0.764	a ¹	0.584	CR: 0.895
Exlr2	0.810	14.620	0.655	AVE: 0.683
Exlr3	0.807	14.567	0.651	α : 0.863
Exlr4	0.918	16.491	0.843	
Exploitation				
Exp1	0.915	a	0.837	
Exp2	0.915	26.890	0.837	CR: 0.958
Exp3	0.951	30.182	0.903	AVE: 0.852
Exp4	0.912	24.525	0.832	α : 0.945
Sourcing Flexibility				
SF1	0.821	a	0.674	CR: 0.884
SF2	0.834	15.993	0.696	AVE: 0.717
SF3	0.884	16.584	0.782	α : 0.816
Operating System Flexibility				
OSF1	0.925	a	0.855	CR: 0.967
OSF2	0.943	31.257	0.890	AVE : 0.878
OSF3	0.970	34.678	0.940	α : 0.950
OSF4	0.909	27.605	0.827	
Distribution Flexibility				
DF1	0.825	a	0.680	CR: 0.931
DF2	0.953	21.384	0.909	AVE: 0.818
DF3	0.931	20.945	0.867	α : 0.863
Information System Flexibility				CR: 0.714
ISF1	0.911	a	0.830	AVE: 0.556
ISF2	0.915	11.083	0.831	α : 0.871
IT Knowledge				
ITK1	0.677	a	0.458	CR: 0.901
ITK2	0.828	12.677	0.685	AVE: 0.568
ITK3	0.785	12.125	0.616	α : 0.842
ITK4	0.784	12.119	0.615	
IT Operations				
ITOp1	0.720	11.248	0.519	CR: 0.852
ITOp2	0.703	11.005	0.494	AVE: 0.569
ITOp3	0.766	11.870	0.586	α : 0.891
ITOp4	0.785	12.125	0.616	
ITOp5	0.784	12.119	0.615	
ITOp6	0.828	12.677	0.685	
IT Objects				
ITOb1	0.812	a	0.659	CR: 0.902
ITOb2	0.885	17.664	0.783	AVE: 0.756
ITOb3	0.908	17.957	0.824	α : 0.952
ITOb4	0.784	12.119	0.615	
ITOb5	0.828	12.677	0.685	

Before assessing fit of the structural model, the second-order constructs must be evaluated by analyzing the factor loadings, the R^2 , CR and AVE of each higher-order construct's dimension. In addition, we have to take into account the fit indicators (RMSEA, NFI, IFI, CFI and AGFI (Bentler and Bonett, 1980). The results (see Table 3) show the validity of all second-order constructs.

Table 3: CFA of second-order constructs

Factors	Standardized parameters	t-values	R ²	Scale reliability
Supply Chain Ambidexterity				CR:0.940
Exploitation	0.918	a	0.844	AVE: 0.887
Exploration	0.965	21.001	0.931	α: 0.901
CFI 0.964; NFI 0.957; IFI 0.964; GFI 0.921; AGFI 0.842; RMSEA 0.05				
Supply Chain Flexibility				
Sourcing Flexibility	0.528	a	0.379	
Operating System Flexibility	0.688	7.147	0.573	CR: 0.812
Distribution Flexibility	0.865	7.336	0.748	AVE: 0.523
Information System Flexibility	0.770	7.368	0.604	α: 0.920
CFI 0.992; NFI 0.973; IFI 0.992; GFI 0.902; AGFI 0.889; RMSEA 0.05				

The approach of Voorhees et al. (2016) was followed to measure construct-level discriminant validity. Firstly, Fornell and Larcker's (1981) procedure was used. As all AVEs values are greater than the correlations of the constructs, the results confirm discriminant validity (see Table 4). Second, heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratios were determined for each pair of

constructs (Henseler et al., 2015). The ratios, displayed in Table 5, take values below 0.85 for each pairing, also confirming discriminant validity. Lastly, the procedure of Szulanski (1996) and Howell (1987) was used to analyze the discriminant validity of the items. We compared the correlations in the CFA to the correlation values for perfect correlation. It is imperative that correlation values be higher than the values obtained and, as seen in the results, that the criterion be met for each and every case; as such items ensure discriminant validity.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9.	Mean	D.T.
1.Exlr	0.826									5.780	1.254
2.Exlp	0.590**	0.923								5.835	1.205
3.SF	0.405**	0.365**	0.847							6.423	1.102
4.OSF	0.421**	0.427**	0.373**	0.937						6.330	1.195
5.DF	0.455**	0.347**	0.402**	0.448**	0.904					6.553	0.955
6.ISF	0.511**	0.410**	0.430**	0.408**	0.350**	0.746				6.545	0.988
7.ITK	0.173**	0.296**	0.300	0.338**	0.371**	0.306	0.754			4.617	1.676
8.ITOp	0.210**	0.231**	0.487**	0.451**	0.411**	0.385**	0.436**	0.754		4.617	1.948
9.ITOb	0.196**	0.204**	0.425**	0.414**	0.403**	0.322*	0.340**	0.430**	0.869	3.626	2.303

Table 5: HTMT ratio

HTMT	Exlr	Exlp	SF	OSF	DF	ISF	ITK	ITOp	ITOb
Exlr									
Exlp	0.837								
SF	0.639	0.499							
OSF	0.593	0.521	0.506						
DF	0.682	0.451	0.581	0.577					
ISF	0.655	0.455	0.531	0.449	0.411				
ITK	0.298	0.441	0.497	0.500	0.584	0.412			
ITOp	0.338	0.322	0.754	0.623	0.605	0.484	0.736		
ITOb	0.380	0.342	0.793	0.689	0.715	0.488	0.691	0.817	

3.3 Common Method Variance

The appropriateness of the measures was further guaranteed by rigorous testing for common method bias that employed both procedural and statistical methods (Podsakoff et al., 2003). First, variables were scrambled to prevent respondents from intuiting the research model

and questions, as it reduced the likelihood that they would adjust their answers to what they believed were the expected results. We kept informants' identities confidential and pre-tested the survey to eliminate ambiguity and ensure that the survey was easy to understand. In addition to the procedural measures we took to avoid common method bias, we assessed the extent to which this bias might have affected our results by using Harman's one-factor test (Podsakoff and Organ, 1986). We conducted an exploratory factor analysis of all construct items with the intent of eliminating the possibility that we might obtain a single factor that explains the bulk of the variance. If most of the variance were explained by the first factor, bias would exist, but in this analysis, the first factor explained only 20.776% of the variance; the rest was distributed evenly across the other factors (15.276%, 11.037%, 5.659%, 4.951%, 4.283%, 3.297%, 2.891%, and 2.691%). We conclude, then, that the potential of common method bias is low.

3.4. Hypotheses testing

To verify the different model hypotheses, we performed hierarchical regression analysis with STATA v.14 software, a methodology used to test moderating effect (Gu et al., 2014; Tamayo-Torres et al., 2010). In the first model, an OLS regression analysis was calculated with the SCF as a dependent variable and only the control variables (type of respondent, industry, and company size) were introduced as independent variables. We chose to introduce type of respondent and industry as dummy variables because this form of specification allows us to detect which category or categories of each variable are significant (the categories used were the same as those used in the sample description in Table 1). Firm size was introduced as a continuous variable, measured with the log firm size (measured via the number of workers). However, none of the control variables were significant.

In the second model, the first explanatory variable, SC ambidexterity, was introduced. The moderator variable, IT competence was introduced in the third model. We added the term representing the interaction effect between SC ambidexterity and IT competence to the fourth model. This multiplicative term included in the equation creates problems of multicollinearity, since it correlates with the independent variables that compose it. According to the recommendation of Jaccard et al. (1990), the variables that compose the multiplicative term are considered relative to their mean to avoid the problem of multicollinearity. To ensure that the results are not affected by multicollinearity, the variance inflation factors (VIF) were calculated for all regressions, and in all cases they obtained levels well below the recommended maximum, thus indicating that the results are not affected by multicollinearity. The results of the hierarchical regression analysis are presented in Table 6. To verify the adequacy of the linear specification, we calculate the RESET (Regression Specification Error Test) Test (Ramsey, 1969), which

enables the detection of possible specification errors. The results obtained, as seen in Table 6, show that our model is correctly specified.

Finally, the Durbin–Wu–Hausman test was conducted to evaluate the presence of endogeneity (Davidson and MacKinnon, 1993, pp. 237-242). We first regressed SC ambidexterity and IT competence on SCF and obtained the residuals for them. We then performed an augmented regression by including all the main effects and the residuals of the first regression. As none of the regression coefficients for the two residuals were significant ($\alpha = 0.10$), we concluded that endogeneity is not an issue in our model.

Table 6: Effect of SC ambidexterity on SCF

	Supply Chain Flexibility											
	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3			Model 4		
	Coef.	t value	power	Coef.	t value	power	Coef.	t value	power	Coef.	t value	power
Constant	3.040*	(2.09)		-0.214	(-0.14)		-0.528	(-0.36)		-0.369	(-0.26)	
dummyInformant1	0	(omitted)		0	(omitted)		0	(omitted)		0	(omitted)	
dummyInformant2	0.516	(0.51)		0.646	(0.68)		0.620	(0.66)		0.604	(0.66)	
dummyInformant3	-0.553	(-0.49)		-0.321	(-0.30)		-0.303	(-0.29)		-0.214	(-0.21)	
dummyIndustry1	-0.054	(-0.03)		0.077	(0.05)		-0.199	(-0.12)		-0.143	(-0.09)	
dummyIndustry2	0.359	(0.22)		0.385	(0.25)		0.261	(0.17)		0.393	(0.27)	
dummyIndustry3	0.845	(0.59)		0.875	(0.64)		0.496	(0.37)		0.619	(0.47)	
dummyIndustry4	0.425	(0.30)		0.331	(0.24)		0.189	(0.14)		0.296	(0.23)	
dummyIndustry5	0.357	(0.27)		0.486	(0.38)		0.328	(0.26)		0.241	(0.20)	
dummyIndustry6	0.103	(0.10)		0.016	(0.02)		-0.290	(-0.30)		-0.258	(-0.28)	
dummyIndustry7	0.263	(0.28)		0.198	(0.22)		-0.015	(-0.02)		0.017	(0.02)	
dummyIndustry8	0.886	(1.03)		0.959	(1.17)		0.842	(1.05)		0.741	(0.95)	
dummyIndustry9	1.021	(1.14)		0.771	(0.90)		0.455	(0.54)		0.345	(0.42)	
dummyIndustry10	0	(omitted)		0	(omitted)		0	(omitted)		0	(omitted)	
Log Firm Size	0.252*	(2.35)	0.650	0.255*	(2.50)	0.704	0.209*	(2.08)	0.545	0.130	(1.30)	0.254
SC Ambidexterity				0.519***	(5.60)	0.900	0.370***	(3.75)	0.962	0.385***	(3.99)	0.978
IT Competence							0.301***	(3.76)	0.963	0.161*	(1.86)	0.460
IT Competence * SC Ambidexterity										0.219***	(3.89)	0.972
R ²	0.043			0.137			0.177			0.219		
Adjusted R ²	0.003			0.098			0.137			0.178		
F	1.08			3.51***			4.42***			5.34***		
Change in R ²	0.094			0.094			0.04			0.042		
Ramsey RESET Test	F (3, 286) = 0.04			F (3, 285) = 2.57			F (3, 284) = 0.30			F (3, 283) = 1.34		

To complete verification of the moderation hypothesis, once a significant moderating effect was found, the strength and nature of the interaction term had to be confirmed, as indicated by Jaccard et al. (1990). An additional regression analysis was thus performed to evaluate the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable so as to distinguish different levels of the moderating variable. Following the recommendation of Jaccard et al. (1990), the observations have a high point-value in the moderating variable when they register values higher than its mean, while the low level of this variable includes the cases that register values below the mean. The results of this analysis are shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Effect of strategy of SC ambidexterity on SCF for different levels of IT competence

	Model 5 (n=162)	Model 6 (n= 140)
	High IT Competence	Low IT Competence
SC Ambidexterity	0,354*** (4,795)	0,076 (0,892)
R ²	0,126	0,006
Adjusted R ²	0,120	0,001
F	22,995	0,796

***p<0.00, **p < 0.01, *p<0.05

The results confirm Hypothesis 1 of the model ($\beta = 0.315$; $t = 5.752$; $p < 0.01$), providing empirical support for the thesis that SC ambidexterity improves the SC's ability to recognize market changes and thereby enable the firm to react to them. Second, the results also support H2, as IT competence moderates the relationship between SC ambidexterity and SCF. The results indicate

that the positive relationship between these two variables is moderated by IT competence when competence is high ($\beta= 0.354$; $t=4.795$; $p < 0.01$). Figure 2 represents the moderating effect of IT competence.

Figure 2: Moderating Effect of IT Competence

3.5. Post-hoc analysis

To explore the robustness of our findings, we re-ran the proposed model with several modifications. The first alternative model was tested to explore whether the relationship between SC ambidexterity and SCF is quadratic (i.e., a U-shaped relationship or an inverted one). As Appendix E shows, the results confirm that the relationship between the two variables is not quadratic but linear, as we theorized. The second alternative model proposed that the relationship between SC ambidexterity and SCF is mediated by IT competence. This model was examined using a SEM model with EQS 6.3. The results are shown in Figure 3 of Appendix E. The fit indices of this second model show that it does not explain the data well, confirming that our model is the best explanation of the data.

4. Discussion and implications

4.1 Discussion of the results

This study uses a resource orchestration approach to theorize and empirically test how the joint deployment of SC ambidexterity and IT competence is related to SCF. First, the results show that SC ambidexterity has a direct and positive effect on SCF. The positive effect indicates that implementing practices for the exploitation of existing knowledge and capabilities simultaneously with practices of exploration and creation of new competences and capabilities improves the SC's ability to detect changes in the environment and accelerate reactions to them. This conclusion is especially important because the earlier literature usually relates only exploration practices to achievement of flexibility (Miller et al. 2006), whereas this study provides important empirical demonstration that combining these practices with others that tend to refinement and efficiency of current competences increases SCF. This is one of the few studies to relate both exploration and exploitation to improvement of flexibility, indicating that the SC's capability for adaptation and reaction to changes in the environment requires not only innovative practices and experimentation with new ideas and knowledge but also their combination with practices based on existing strategies and knowledge. This result is consistent with the latest findings in the literature on operations, which show that ambidexterity has beneficial effects in this area (Kristal et al., 2010; Patel et al., 2012; Kilpi et al., 2018). It is also consistent with the literature that relates different learning mechanisms to adaptation to the environment (Santos-Vijande et al., 2012).

Second, SC ambidexterity has been found to complement high IT competence and can have synergistic outcomes in the form of SCF. Nevertheless, IT competence without SC ambidexterity does not enhance SC performance. Put simply, SC ambidexterity can directly impacts SCF, and the presence of high IT competence accentuates this effect. This result is empirical proof of the ROT proposal that “the whole is greater than the sum of its parts”. Given the greater competition for the efficient use of resources in the current market, finding complementary relationships and interaction effects between different capabilities is of vital importance. Investment in and improvement of IT competence has been a business constant in recent years, and this result improves understanding of how this capability is connected to others in the SC. The added value IT competence contributes to the relationship between ambidexterity, and SCF is generated because better information sharing helps suppliers and distributors align their plans with the needs of the firm and enables SC partners to be better prepared for changing needs, which results in increased SCF (Chiang et al., 2012). This result converges with the argument that the value of IT assets can only be realized through their appropriate use with other complementary investments (Oh et al., 2012; Mikalef and Pateli, 2017).

As to the explanatory power of the model tested, we should focus on the R^2 of Model 4 (0.235) and the R^2 of Model 5 (0.354). These values are acceptable compared to the R^2 values obtained in past empirical studies of SCM (Sacristán-Díaz et al., 2018). The values show that

good synchronization of SC ambidexterity and IT competence, which has been shown empirically to occur when IT competence is high, enables the firm to influence the level of SCF by more than 35%. This result highlights the importance of a precise marriage of knowledge management-related competences to gain a competitive advantage in the SC context. Furthermore, the post-hoc analysis performed reinforces the explanatory power of the theoretical model.

4.2. Theoretical implications

This study constitutes one of the first attempts to comprehensively investigate the value of IT for ambidexterity in the context of SCM. We have developed a model depicting the process of managing SC ambidexterity and IT competence with the intention of creating a sustained competitive advantage in the form of SCF. The second contribution relates to the study of resource complementarities in SCM. We have deepened knowledge of how a firm's assets and capabilities should be managed relative to its SC partners so as to achieve a flexible SC. The results on the reinforcing effects of IT competence highlight the complexity of IT and the need to integrate it properly into SCM. ROT has been applied to explain the relationships between the model variables. This study follows the recommendation of Spina et al. (2016) to borrow an "external grand theory" to explain operations research models. This approach enables us to develop a solid contribution to the purchasing and supply management literature. In doing so, this study makes a twofold contribution to ROT. First, it answers the call by Sirmon et al. (2011) for more empirical insights into the scope of resource orchestration by detailing how asset orchestration can be operationalized at the SC level. Second, as most studies of ROT are conceptual (Sirmon et al., 2007, 2011), there is a need for empirical studies like ours to verify this theory. Finally, the last theoretical implication shows that SC ambidexterity and IT competence are antecedents and facilitators respectively of SCF. The study thus responds to the call by Rojo et al. (2018) for research that develops a deeper understanding of the antecedents of SCF.

4.3 Practical implications

This study also contributes significantly to business practice. First, as companies operate within markets that demand increasing flexibility, understanding how to foster SCF is crucial, thus it is also critical that managers know what strategies and competences promote improved flexibility. This study demonstrates that exploration and exploitation match in the SC and that managers must implement both practices if they are to achieve a flexible SC. This finding means that efficiency and flexibility are not opposed objectives in SCM.

Second, firms have in recent years invested millions of euros in the attempt to obtain greater profit (Liu et al., 2013; Luzzini et al., 2014). Numerous investments in IT have not,

however, translated into increased profits because managers fail to realize that IT alone does not have a direct effect on a firm's results, but, rather, that it affects them through other capabilities. This paper thus offers a guide which allows managers to invest in IT profitably, as it shows what part of IT's business value consists in its positive impact on SCF. Examining the relationships among flexibility, ambidexterity, and IT competence helps firms discern whether and how much they must invest in developing IT competence to build a flexible SC. Our finding that the relationship between ambidexterity and SCF is amplified when IT competence is high implies that the transmission of IT in SCF occurs when a firm has invested to a high degree in IT, since the effect does not occur for lower and initial levels of this competence. Managers must thus perform a cost-benefit analysis before investing in IT competence intended to achieve a flexible SC.

Finally, studying strategies applied to the SC, as well as the use of the ROT in this area, helps managers recognize that the firm they manage is only a node in a network and that they can create competitive advantage based not only on firm assets but also increasingly from the assets and capabilities of the network in which they operate (Essex et al., 2016; Kähkönen and Lintukangas, 2012). Firms must thus concern themselves with managing not only their own capabilities but also those of the SC to which they belong.

4.4. Limitations and future lines of research

As do all studies, this study has its limitations. First, it focuses on manufacturing firms in Spain, which can limit generalization in other contexts. Second, it uses a single respondent to obtain data, with the risk of common method bias. Although a series of procedural and statistical measures were taken to inhibit this bias, future research might confirm our results with various key respondents, which Junni et al. (2013) recommend for the improvement of ambidexterity studies. Manders et al. (2016) also recommend that, to enable a more precise evaluation of flexibility, future studies should include the views of other SC members. Third, the data used are transversal, so that when analyzing SCF, the possibility exists that a momentary situation in an organization will be analyzed but not long-term capability for flexibility. Fourth, future research should include other variables that precede SCF (such as organizational learning and operational absorptive capacity) (Rojo et al., 2018) so that a more exhaustive picture of the enablers of SCF can be developed. Finally, future studies should analyze the interplay between exploration and exploitation not only at firm level or SC level, individually, but at both levels simultaneously (Stettner and Lavie, 2016).

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Appendix A: Comparison between Absorptive Capacity and Ambidexterity

Absorptive Capacity		Ambidexterity	
Cohen and Levinthal (1989)	The firm ability to identify, assimilate and exploit knowledge from external sources.	O'Reilly and Tushman (2004)	The organization ability to simultaneously pursue both explorative (discontinuous) and exploitative (incremental) innovation.
Cohen and Levinthal (1990)	The firm ability to identify, assimilate and exploit commercial knowledge from external sources.	O'Reilly and Tushman (2008)	The firm ability to simultaneously explore and exploit.
Cohen and Levinthal (1994)	The firm ability to exploit new knowledge from external sources, as well as to accurately predict the nature of future technological advances.	Lubatkin et al. (2006)	Firms "capable of exploiting existing competencies as well as exploring new opportunities with equal dexterity" (p.2)
Szulanski (1996)	The firm ability to evaluate, assimilate and apply successfully the new knowledge for commercial purposes, based on the knowledge base previously existing in the firm.	Cao et al. (2009)	Obtaining a balance between exploration and exploitation, as well as the attempt to maximize both simultaneously
Zahra and George (2002)	Set of organizational routines and strategic processes by which companies acquire, assimilate, transform and exploit knowledge with the intention of creating a dynamic organizational capacity.	Hill and Birkinshaw (2014)	"The capacity to capitalize on an existing set of resources and capabilities while at the same time developing new combinations of resources to meet future market needs" (p.1899)

Appendix B: Comparison between Supply Chain Flexibility and SC resilience

Supply Chain Flexibility		Supply Chain Resilience	
Manders et al. (2017)	“The SC ability to change or react to environmental uncertainty” (p. 973)	Christopher and Rutherford (2004)	The SC ability to return to its original or desired state after being disturbed.
Choy et al. (2008)	“The extent to which the SC linkages are able to adapt to changing business conditions rather than being forced into adapting to a given environment” (p. 2000)	Falasca et al. (2008)	The SC ability to reduce the probabilities of a disruption, to reduce the consequences of those disruptions when they occur and to reduce the time to recover normal performance
Agus (2011)	“The degree to which the supply chain can respond to random fluctuations in demand and supply changes” (p.136)	Guoping and Xinqiu (2010)	The SC ability to return to its original or ideal status under emergency risk environment.
Duclos et al. (2003)	“The SC’s promptness and the degree to which it can adjust its SC speed, destinations and volumes in response to changes in customer demand” (p. 448)	Pettit et al. (2010)	The SC ability to survive, adapt and grow in the face of turbulent change.
Malhotra and MacKelprang (2012)	“A system or network of interrelated external flexibilities (inbound and outbound) and internal manufacturing flexibilities, which taken together support the focal firm’s performance outcomes from a customer-oriented perspective” (p. 181)	Ponis and Koronis (2012)	The ability to proactively plan and design the SC network for anticipating unexpected disruptive (negative events), respond adaptively to disruptions while maintaining control over structure and function and transcending to a post robust state of operations, if possible a more favourable one than that prior to the event, thus gaining a competitive advantage

Appendix C

Supply Chain Ambidexterity (Kristal et al., 2010)

Exploitation

Expl1.-In order to stay competitive, our supply chain managers focus on reducing operational redundancies in our existing processes.

Expl2.-Leveraging of our current supply chain technologies is important to our firm's strategy.

Expl3.-In order to stay competitive, our supply chain managers focus on improving our existing technologies.

Expl4.-Our managers focus on developing stronger competencies in our existing supply chain processes.

Exploration

Exlr1. -We proactively pursue new supply chain solutions.

Exlr2.-We continually experiment to find new solutions that will improve our supply chain.

Exlr3.-To improve our supply chain, we continually explore for new opportunities.

Exlr4.-We are constantly seeking novel approaches in order to solve supply chain problems.

Supply Chain Flexibility (Moon et al.. 2012)

Sourcing Flexibility

SFF1. - Number of available suppliers

SFF2.-Range of products and services provided by major suppliers

SFF3.-Range of suppliers that provide major materials/components/products

Operating System Flexibility

OSF1. - Range of new products or services the firm can develop every year.

OSF2.- Ability to change output volume

OSF3. - Ability to change products and services mix

OSF4. - Ability to adjust manufacturing facilities and processes

Distribution Flexibility

DFF1. - Ability to change storage space, loading capability, and other distribution installations

DFF2. - Ability to change delivery modes

DFF3.-Ability to transfer delivery schedules

Information System Flexibility

ISFF1.- Support of information systems in transportation and distribution management

ISFF2. - Support of information systems in firm inventory management

IT Competence (Tippins and Sohi, 2003)

IT knowledge

ITK1.-Overall, our technical support staff is knowledgeable when it comes to computer-based systems.

ITK2.- Our firm possesses a high degree of computer-based technical expertise.

ITK3.- We are very knowledgeable about new computer-based innovations.

ITK4.- We have the knowledge to develop and maintain computer-based communication links with our customers.

IT operations

ITOp1.- Our firm is skilled at collecting and analyzing market information about our customers via computer-based systems.

ITOp2.-We routinely utilize computer-based systems to access market information from outside databases.

ITOp3.- We have set procedures for collecting customer information from online sources.

ITOp4.- We use computer-based systems to analyze customer and market information.

ITOp5.- We utilize decision-support systems frequently when it comes to managing customer information.

ITOp6.- We rely on computer-based systems to acquire, store, and process information about our customers.

IT objects

ITOb1.- Our company has a formal MIS department.

ITOb2.- Our firm employs a manager whose main duties include the management of our information technology.

ITOb3.- Every year we budget a significant amount of funds for new information technology hardware and software.

ITOb4.- Our firm creates customized software applications when the need arises.

ITOb5.- Our firm's members are linked by a computer network.

APPENDIX D: Exploratory Factor Analysis

Items	Factor1 : Exlp	Factor2 : Exlr	Factor 3: SF	Factor4 : OSF	Factor5 : DF	Factor 6: ITK	Factor 7: ISF	Factor 8: ITOp	Factor 9: ITOb
Exlp1	0.949								
Exlp2	0.961								
Exlp3	0.980								
Exlp4	0.925								
Exlr1		0.791							
Exlr2		0.976							
Exlr3		0.947							
Exlr4		0.911							
SF1			0.844						
SF2			0.857						
SF3			0.858						
OSF1				0.933					
OSF2				0.947					
OSF3				0.988					
OSF4				0.970					
DF1					0.849				
DF2					0.857				
DF3					0.857				
ITK1						0.865			
ITK2						0.851			
ITK3						0.758			
ITK4						0.909			
ISF1							0.831		
ISF2							0.861		
ITOp1								0.780	
ITOp2								0.817	
ITOp3								0.819	
ITOp4								0.772	
ITOp5								0.846	
ITOp6								0.762	
ITOb1									0.751
ITOb2									0.755
ITOb3									0.711
ITOb4									0.718
ITOb5									0.780

Appendix E: Post hoc analysis

Alternative Model 1:

	Supply Chain Flexibility		
	Coef.	t value	power
Constant	1.248	(0.59)	
dummyInformant1	0	(omitted)	
dummyInformant2	0.538	(0.59)	
dummyInformant3	-0.288	(-0.28)	
dummyIndustry1	-0.226	(-0.14)	
dummyIndustry2	0.259	(0.18)	
dummyIndustry3	0.509	(0.39)	
dummyIndustry4	0.190	(0.15)	
dummyIndustry5	0.131	(0.11)	
dummyIndustry6	-0.284	(-0.30)	
dummyIndustry7	-0.038	(-0.04)	
dummyIndustry8	0.692	(0.88)	
dummyIndustry9	0.295	(0.36)	
dummyIndustry10	0	(omitted)	
Log Firm Size	0.122	(1.22)	0.229
SC Ambidexterity	-0.220	(-0.38)	0.066
SC Ambidexterity ²	0.057	(1.05)	0.183
IT Competence	0.168*	(1.94)	0.489
IT Competence * SC Ambidexterity	0.221***	(3.92)	0.974
R ²	0.182		
Adjusted R ²	0.168		
F	5.07***		

Figure 3: Alternative Model 2

Acknowledgements

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